

Metal Complexes of 2-Hydroxy 4-Methyl 5-Chloro Acetophenone Oxime

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2-hydroxy 4-methyl 5-chloro acetophenone oxime has been prepared, purified and used as chelatometric reagent for copper and nickel. The structures of complexes have been established by conductometric methods and by elemental analysis. Infra-red study of the complexes have been done with a view to study how far the IR spectra help in establishing the chelation and structure of complexes.

Metal complexes of acetophenone oxime^{1,2} have been widely studied with respect to their applications in various fields. With the expectation that the substitution in the phenyl ring of the acetophenone may make it specific to certain cations, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime has been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used in these investigations were either AnalaR or E. Merck's guaranteed reagent quality. The conductivity measurements were performed on a null detector type conductivity bridge with magic eye. Infra-red absorption spectra were recorded on an automatic Perkin-Elmer 137 infracord spectrophotometer with rock salt optics in KBr phase at slow legend.

Preparation of the Reagent : *m*-cresol was chlorinated³ with the modification made in the present work by the use of Al-Hg couple as halogen carrier. The product obtained was 4-chloro-*m*-cresol (m.p. 55°-66°) which was acetylated⁴ with acetic-anhydride to give acetic ester (b.p. 241°-43°). The Fries rearrangement⁵ gave *o*-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone (m.p. 75.5°) only. The ketone was oximated to give 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro acetophenone oxime. It was recrystallised several times from ethanol (m.p. 145-46°).

Reactions with metal ions : A 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent (HMCA) was employed for the tests. The precipitate or colour formation along with the pH range were noted and recorded in Table 1. The following ions were found to give no precipitate or colour :—silver (I), thallium (I & III), mercury (II), lead (II), cadmium (II), bismuth (II), arsenic (III), antimony (III), tin (II & IV), aluminium (III), chromium (III), zinc (II), manganese (II), alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, sulphates, phosphates, borates, fluorides, oxalates and nitrates etc.

Preparation of copper and nickel complexes : Copper and nickel complexes have been precipitated at pH 5 and 8 respectively. The precipitates were washed with hot water followed by ethanol to remove the adhering ions. Precipitates were insoluble

in non-polar solvents but were sparingly soluble in dioxane. They decomposed at 250° without melting.

TABLE 1

Sr.No.	Metal Ion	pH range	Interaction precipitate or colour
1.	copper (II)	2.5-10	buff coloured precipitate
2.	nickel (II)	6-10	green coloured precipitate
3.	cobalt (II)	6-10	yellow coloured precipitate
4.	vanadium (IV)	3-9	pink and yellow precipitates
5.	uranium (VI)	6-9	yellow colour
6.	iron (II & III)	5-8	violet colour
7.	titanium (IV)	4-8	light brown colour

Composition : The composition of the complexes has been determined conductometrically. The Job's method⁶ of continuous variation (Fig. 2) and reverse and direct titration (Fig. 1) indicated a 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio. Carbon and hydrogen were estimated

Fig. 1 : Curve A : Direct titration [Cu(II) 0.02M and HMCA 0.02M]
 Curve B : Direct titration [Cu(II) 0.005M and HMCA 0.01M]
 Curve C : Reverse titration [HMCA 0.02M and Cu(II) 0.02M]

by usual procedures, nitrogen by micro method with the use of Potassium bromate⁷ and metal was determined by complexometric titrations with EDTA⁸. The results of analysis are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Complex		Carbon %	Hydrogen %	Nitrogen %	Metal %
Copper complex	Calc.	46.91	3.93	6.08	13.87
	Found	47.06	3.94	6.34	13.80
Nickel complex	Calc.	47.41	3.97	6.12	12.67
	Found	48.14	3.93	6.43	12.91

Infra-red Spectra : Infra-red spectra of the ligand and complexes are recorded from 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} in Table 3.

Fig. 2 : Job's method : Cu(II) 0.02M and HMCA 0.02M.

DISCUSSION

As conductometric and elemental analysis indicate the metal—ligand ratio in these complexes as 1 : 2 the structure which can be assigned to metal complexes can be as below :— (structure No. I).

The spectral data indicate that the absorption frequencies are perturbed on complex formation. In ligand the first maxima at 3400 cm^{-1} leads to conclusion of intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁹ (structure II). The shift of this maxima to 2900 cm^{-1} in copper and to 2850 cm^{-1} in nickel chelate is surely due to chelation⁹. A weak maxima at 1725 cm^{-1} , assigned to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ grouping, shifts to 1700 cm^{-1} in chelates and its intensity is also reduced. Another peak at 1320 cm^{-1} which shifts to 1330 cm^{-1} in complexes is also conclusive to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching coupled with $-\text{O}-\text{H}$ deformation¹⁰. The medium peaks at 1230 and 930 cm^{-1} in ligand has been assigned to $\text{N}-\text{O}$ stretching vibrations which shift to 1245 and 960 cm^{-1} in copper chelate and to 1250 and 970 cm^{-1} in nickel chelate¹¹⁻¹³. These changes in the absorption frequencies for $\text{C}=\text{N}$ grouping and $\text{N}-\text{O}$ stretching vibrations confirm

TABLE 3

Absorption frequencies of bis-HMCA metal chelates

Sr.No.	Pure ligand cm^{-1}	Copper chelate cm^{-1}	Nickel chelate cm^{-1}	Possible assignment
1.	3400(s)	2900(s)	2850(s)	—O—H str.
2.	1725(w)	1700(vw)	1700(vw)	$\text{C}=\text{N}$
3.	1640(m)	1635(w)	1635(w)	Aromatic phenyl ring
	1630(m)	1625(s)	1625(s)	showing conjugation.
4.	1560(m)	1530(m)	1540(m)	Phenyl ring vibration.
5.	1500(m)	1475(s)	1475(s)	
	1450(m)	1450(s)	1450(s)	$\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$
	1380(s)	1400(s)	1400(s)	
		1380(s)	1390(s)	
6.	1320(m)	1330(m)	1330(m)	$\text{C}=\text{N}$ coupled with O—H str.
7.	1270(m)	1290(m)	1280(m)	$\text{C}-\text{H}$ in plane
	1260(m)		1290(m)	
8.	1230(m)	1245(m)	1250(m)	$\text{N}-\text{O}$ str.
9.	1180(s)	1200(s)	1200(s)	$\text{C}-\text{O}$ str.
10.	1090(s)	1090(s)	1090(s)	O—H def.
11.	1030(s)	1030(s)	1030(s)	Benzene ring breathing
12.	930(m)	960(m)	970(m)	$\text{N}-\text{O}$ str.
13.	880(s)	880(s)	880(s)	1-2-4-5 tetrasubstituted benzene ring.
14.	815(m)	810(s)	820(s)	Two adjacent free hydrogen atoms.
15.	780(m)	750(s)	760(s)	$\text{C}-\text{Cl}$
16.	740(m)	730(w)	720(w)	$\text{C}-\text{H}$ out of plane
	690(s)	720(w)	685(m)	
		700(s)		

the donation of a lone pair from nitrogen atom to metal to form chelate. Similarly there is a shift in the frequency of C-O stretching vibration from 1180 to 1200 cm^{-1} which can also be assigned to chelate formation.

The absorption frequencies of various groups and bonds recorded in Table 3 in the molecules of ligand (HMCA) and the copper and nickel complexes confirm the structures (I & II).

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